

FACE3DBIOMARK: A LOW-COST SOLUTION TO COMPUTE 3D FACIAL BIOMARKERS FOR DIAGNOSING CONDITIONS WITH ASSOCIATED FACIAL DYSMORPHOLOGIES

Álvaro Heredia-Lidón¹, Alejandro Moñux-Bernal¹, Luis M. Echeverry-Quiceno²,
Neus Martínez-Abadías², Xavier Sevillano¹

¹La Salle - Universitat Ramon Llull. HER - Human-Environment Research Group. Barcelona, Spain

²Universitat de Barcelona (UB). BEECA, Facultat de Biologia. Barcelona, Spain

Facial dysmorphologies are associated with a wide range of diseases and are emerging as potential diagnostic biomarkers in rare, psychotic and neurodevelopmental disorders [1]. Each disorder presents a distinctive facial pattern that, either subtle or severe, is unique and often sex-specific. Despite intensive research to reveal genetic biomarkers, first-time diagnosis is mainly based on clinical interviews, and health-care professionals still use qualitative visual assessments and simple anthropometric measurements to guide diagnosis. To optimize this process, quantitative and objective tools for assessing 3D facial dysmorphologies are needed.

Here, we introduce Face3DBiomark, a low-cost, multi-platform and easy-to-use tool for capturing high-quality 3D facial meshes and computing facial biomarkers. In comparison to other methods that rely on high-end equipment, like laser or MRI scanners, our system is based on a smartphone, so it could be readily translated into the clinical practice.

The architecture of our proposal comprises two main elements (Figure 1). First, a smartphone app to capture 3D facial scans and a web-based interface to collect clinical data of the subjects. And second, a dedicated backend server to securely store clinical and facial data in a non-relational database and to automatically *i)* process 3D facial meshes, *ii)* run deep learning models for 3D facial landmarking, and *iii)* compute facial biomarkers using geometric morphometrics.

Facial meshes are acquired via the iPhone’s TrueDepth infrared camera using the open 3D modelling Standard Cyborg API, and then automatically processed for facial segmentation, orientation normalization and remeshing using the screened Poisson method [2]. Facial landmarks are detected leveraging multiview consensus CNNs [3], achieving an error below 1mm at best when compared to manual landmarks.

Finally, based on the landmarks 3D coordinates, Generalized Procrustes Analysis and Euclidean Distance Matrix Analysis identify statistically significant global and local differences in facial morphology between controls and patients.

Thus, Face3DBiomark is a promising tool to reduce the

(a) Workflow of Face3DBiomark

(b) Examples of 3D facial meshes

(c) Examples of 3D landmarking

Fig. 1. Face3DBiomark workflow and examples.

diagnostic odyssey and improve the prognosis and quality of life of people with rare and neurodevelopmental disorders.

1. REFERENCES

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